

OPTIMAL WIRELESS POWER TRANSFER FOR ELECTRICAL VEHICLE BATTERY CHARGING

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ABSTRACT:

Because the WPT approach eliminates the need for physical contact between the car and the charging equipment, it eliminates the hassle and risk associated with the conventional conductive method. Attaining parity in power and efficiency between the conductive charging technique and the innovative WPT technology is the primary goal. Evaluation and study of AC side soft-switching inverters for use in electric vehicles (EVs). A dearth of thorough studies assessing and evaluating the performance of soft-switching inverters persists, despite the many claims that these approaches may outperform the traditional hard-switching inverter. Analytical calculations, operations, and controls aimed at reducing loss were used to compare the efficiency of several types of soft-switching inverters. Inverters that are capable of zero-voltage-transition (ZVT) or zero-current-transition (ZCT) operation have been shown to operate very efficiently. We use MATLABR2013a/SIMULINK to do the simulation. The suggested hardware configuration was built around the PIC16F877a microcontroller.

Keywords: Zero Current Transition, Wireless Power Transfer, and Zero Voltage Transition.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Over 60% of the world's main energy needs are still met by transportation and power production, with most of that energy coming from fossil fuels. This is despite the growing concern for the environment and the need to

conserve resources. There will inevitably be a widespread shift towards renewable energy sources and electric vehicles (EVs). Particularly in the realm of public transit, this is becoming more common in a number of nations. This change would ease pollution management to a certain degree by moving the emission sources from dispersed individual automobiles to a small number of centralised power plants. But things aren't quite as they should be. The primary source of power for electric vehicles is still fossil fuels in many nations. That would defeat the point of installing EVs in the first place, as pollution would just be transferred to other areas without being much reduced. Second, we still don't have the technology in batteries to

charging the battery often helps EV owners overcome range anxiety, which is the concern that their electric vehicle won't have enough juice to complete a medium-to long-distance journey. On top of that, the electric vehicle would be unable to move for a few minutes to a few hours as it charged, all dependent on the charging method and starting state of charge (SOC). The EV's adaptability is severely hampered by such an extensive range.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Renewable energy sources and electric vehicles (EVs) have the ability to significantly reduce transportation-related and power-generation-related carbon emissions. Among the many potential effects and advantages of widespread EV adoption is the possibility that they may facilitate the incorporation of renewable energy sources into preexisting power systems. Electric vehicles, the power grid, and the incorporation of renewable energy sources are the topics of this paper's literature evaluation. There is a

discussion of the literature's essential assumptions and methodologies. There is a survey of the effects of EVs on the grid, the environment, and the economy. Research on electric vehicles' capacity to incorporate renewable energy sources is extensive, and what little there is suggests that EVs can drastically cut down on the amount of renewable energy that ends up in the power grid's surplus. Research on wind-electric vehicle interactions is far more extensive than that on PV and EVs from solar sources. Suggestions for further study are included in the paper's last section. Battery chargers, charging power levels, and infrastructure for plug-in electric cars and hybrids are reviewed in this article. It also touches on the present state and implementation of these topics. Both on-board and off-board charger systems are available, and the power flow direction may be either bidirectional or unidirectional. By eliminating one-way charging, we can reduce hardware needs and make connecting a breeze. Injecting energy from batteries back into the grid is made possible via bidirectional charging. Conventional on-board chargers have limited power output due to considerations of space, weight, and affordability. These issues may be circumvented by integrating them with the electric drive. The need for and expense of on-board energy storage decreases when charging infrastructure is readily available. Both conductive and inductive on-board charging technologies are available. There are less physical constraints on the design of an off-board charger, allowing for faster charging rates. We talk about the three different types of power: convenience, primary, and quick. Roadbed charging and other future-oriented features are shown. In this article, we provide, analyse, and assess several power level chargers and infrastructure configurations according to a number of criteria, including power, charging time and location, cost, and equipment. To improve charger performance and reduce driver wait times at PHEV charging stations, we suggest a battery replacement method. We optimise the scheduling of charger operations at a charging station with the battery replacement

plan. The goals of the scheduling are to maximise the number of PHEVs that can be supplied while minimising the cost of power use. Furthermore, we provide a quantitative analysis of how faulty data transmission affects the scheduling

performance. On top of that, we help the grid operator out by creating and solving a multistage stochastic programming model that minimises the cost of electricity supply. The optimisation of supply includes issues with renewable energy source development and the use of energy storage technologies. Developing and deploying electric vehicles (EVs) has been prompted by the requirement to decrease carbon emissions and usage of fossil fuels. The growing number of electric vehicles on the road will have a major impact on the stability of power grids. At the moment, plug-in mode and battery exchange (BE) mode are the two most viable options for charging electric vehicles. Research on the effects of plug-in electric vehicles has been extensive. Nevertheless, there has been very little investigation into BE mode. Estimating the reliability effect of electric vehicles operating in BE mode is the objective of this article. To begin, two credible databases are used to gather data about EV user behaviour when in BE mode. Built on top of a modified version of a technique initially intended for plug-in mode, the behaviour extraction approach is tailored to BE mode. The next step is to use a new reliability metric called User Demand Not Satisfied (UDNS) to examine power system dependability from the perspective of both the power system and the electric vehicle (EV) customers. Integrating energy storage systems (ESS) is the basis for the algorithm that is used to construct the reliability evaluation method. The numerical findings show that power system reliability characteristics may be significantly improved by integrating EVs utilising BE mode. To allow effective and economical grid operations, future smart grids will incorporate flexible supply-demand management and a large penetration of renewable energy. Although renewable energy sources are cleaner and less expensive, they also increase supply

uncertainty because of how unpredictable they are. Therefore, it is practically important to study how to make the most of renewable energy using the supply-demand model of future smart grids, where power users and generators can adapt their energy provisioning and demand in response to system state data that accounts for the unpredictability of renewable power. We focus on home smart networks that include a centralised renewable energy source and how to schedule energy efficiently while keeping costs low. Our scheduling problem seeks to do two things: 1) determine how much of a tradeoff there is between the system-wide benefit and the cost of using renewable energy, and 2) assess how much of an impact renewable energy volatility has on that tradeoff. In order to find the best way to use renewable energy and make the related energy scheduling choices, we also provide distributed algorithms that are efficient in terms of compute.

3.CONVENTIONAL METHOD:

Wireless power transfer can make an extraordinary change in the field of the electrical engineering which eliminates the use of conventional copper cables and current carrying wires. Based on a concept, the project is developed to transfer power within a small range. The power is transferred without any connection. The maximum distance that modern wireless power transmitters can carry current is one foot. Use in tiny consumer electronics is possible at these distances. Famous for his

outstanding work with alternating current (AC) production, Nikola Tesla—also known as the "Father of Wireless"—was the first to think about transmitting power wirelessly and the first to show that it could be done.

3.1 Project Benefits:

- Elimination of cords on the ground that make tripping hazards.
- Allows no wire installation.
- A necessary step towards consumer wireless power.

4.PROPOSED METHODOLOGY:

Four Points on Context and Reasoning: The alternating current (ac) voltage at the coil's input comes from an AC source. However, the frequency is raised from 50 Hz to several sources before it is directly applied to the coil by a high frequency transformation. Achieving extended distance and reducing power usage are both achieved efficiently by doing this. By utilising switching devices, the frequency transformation can be accomplished by alternately generating pulses and feeding them into the transmitting inductor (primary coil). The voltage flow through this coil is converted into electromagnetic waves, which are then transmitted to the receiving inductor (secondary coil).

Fig: 1. Block diagram of WPT

Fig 2.Frequency transfer system

The receiving inductor, also known as the secondary coil, is used to capture the electromagnetic waves that generate the alternating current (AC) voltage inside the coil. The rectifier and filter circuits transformed the alternating current (AC) into direct current (DC) and removed the unwanted components from the output. A steady DC voltage was supplied by this circuit in the past. A voltage regulator is necessary to transform the uncontrolled voltage received into a regulated DC voltage at the output. The load that drives it receives this controlled voltage.

4.1 Justification For Thestudy:

Devices capable of wirelessly transmitting electricity have become more important as time has progressed. Research on appropriate methodologies for use in the creation of such devices is now at a high level of activity. This is significant for the reasons that follow. Adaptability: WPT will do away with the need for wires and conductors. Power may be sent wirelessly from a power source to devices, eliminating the clutter that comes with cables and allowing for more items to be powered without being in close proximity to the source. Concerns about safety have arisen in response

to the widespread electrification of previously unconnected regions, since exposed conductors pose a significant risk of electric shock to humans and other animals. In order to avoid electrical shocks, WPT will remove these conductors.

The usage of WPT will make gadgets easier to use, which is a major convenience. For instance, instead of undergoing surgery every time the battery life of a pacemaker runs out, it is possible to recharge it. Not only is this a more convenient alternative, but it will also reduce surgical expenses.

Dependability: It happens all the time that people are using a gadget and then it dies, and there isn't a power outlet nearby or a cable to charge it. But with WPT, you won't have to worry about running out of juice since your gadgets can be charged wirelessly.

.5.EXISTING SYSTEM:

An increasing amount of time and energy has been devoted to studying the battery switching technique from the vantage points of power engineering and operation research. As an example, consider the scheduling of BCS battery charging as an inventory management

challenge. The goal is to maximise profit or cost while also meeting the expectations of FB. Nonetheless, it was presumed that the charging rate of every CB would remain constant. As an alternative to centralised charging, the best practices for buying and charging batteries were expanded in to find the best charging strategy for local charging and exchanging. While the aforementioned works have shed light on the

best way to implement a battery swapping strategy, they have neglected to address the incorporation of renewable production. While there has been little research into using renewable energy for battery swapping strategies, there have been some similar efforts in the larger area of electric vehicle charging, which has caught the attention of the smart grid community.

Fig 3: Conventional Method

Stage 1 – day-ahead commitment:

The BCS operator only has to make educated guesses about the RTP and quantity of renewable energy production for each time slot (e.g., hour) in the next day. Currently, we are focusing on determining the best buy day-ahead due to the fact that the precise outcomes of these two stochastic processes are not known. electricity from the grid in order to minimise the overall anticipated cost of charging for all of its conceivable implementations. Then, one makes a purchase request to the utility provider for grid electricity for each time slot the following day one day in advance. Step 2 - adjusting in real-time:

At times, the ideal aggregate charging load calculated by the OPD may be unmet by the total available power, which includes both renewable power generation and bought day-ahead grid electricity. When CBs are in a haste to meet some really pressing FB requests, this may occur, for example. The imbalance can

only be remedied by purchasing more grid electricity in real-time. Be aware that the real-time buying market and the day-ahead purchasing market behave differently when it comes to price. Conversely, surplus power would result if, at any given time slot, the OPD determined that the aggregate charging load should be lower than the available power. Inaccurate forecasts for the next day are usually to blame. So, the power company may repurchase this amount at a different price point, ideally very low, to discourage very huge gaps and promote better accuracy for the day ahead.

Concept of Wireless transmission Electric energy:

As a result of the extensive research in WPT, various categories have arisen. WPT can be categorized in terms of efficiency, distance of transmission, power level and size. Classification based on distance of transmission however is more relevant

Fig 4: Classification of WPT

6. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

The technology of wireless charging, also referred to as wireless power transfer (WPT) or inductive power transfer (IPT), has been successfully applied at the low power level, such as applications in the medical field or in small devices such as smart phones. Along with the fast growing interest in electric vehicles (EVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), wireless charging is becoming a new way of charging batteries. In this paper, the design of a WPT system for electrical bus fast wireless charging stations will be presented. The system is composed by a two stage switching power supply, i.e. a multi phase soft-switching

buck converter controlling the output power and a high-frequency resonant full-bridge converter connected to a series-series compensation topology.

6.1 Explanation:

In this proposed WPT system the ac supply is converted into low level dc supply with the help of the ac-dc circuit, after that the dc supply is given to the high frequency switching devices. The secondary side of the system consists of the secondary winding which can receive the transferred power from primary side. After that, the power is converted to the dc form with the help of AC-DC converter and transferred to the battery charging purpose.

Fig 5: Proposed Block Diagram

6.2 Advantages:

In simple terms, zero-voltage switching can be described as the power to the device is turned off or on only when the output voltage is zero volts. This technique functions on pulse width modulation-based (PWM) operations like most other contemporary switching voltage regulators. But the ZVS operation comes into play due to an additional separate phase to the PWM timing.

Another advantage is that this technology uses lower-voltage rating switches, which allows engineers to use other components with higher characteristics such as lower driving currents, higher energy density, and lower conduction losses.

6.3 Soft –Switching Control:

Soft-switching control In order to achieve high-power density, the converter can be designed to operate in discontinuous conducting mode (DCM) such that the passive inductor can be minimized, affecting the converter size. The DCM operation introduces a large current ripple, so it is necessary to interleave multiple phases to cancel the high-frequency switching current ripple, as previously mentioned. Another major advantage of this operation mode is that zero turn-on loss and thus low diode reverse recovery loss can be achieved. However, the DCM operation largely increases turnoff loss because the main switch is turned off at twice the load current or higher. Another important issue is the inductor current parasitic ringing due to the inductor oscillation with the device output capacitance during turn-off. For those reasons in this paper each phase

has been realized by a synchronous buck converter composed by two complementary IGBTs with a snubber capacitor in parallel source.

6.4 Inductive coupling:

Fig 6: inductive wireless power system

One method of transferring electricity between wire coils is known as inductive coupling, electromagnetic induction, or inductive power transfer (IPT). A transformer is formed by the coils of the transmitter and receiver when they are connected together (refer to the figure). According to Ampere's law, a fluctuating magnetic field (B) is produced when an alternating current (AC) flows through the transmitter coil (L1). By use of Faraday's law of induction, an alternating electric field (EMF) (voltage) is produced in the receiver when a magnetic field travels through the receiving coil (L2). The load may be driven directly by the induced alternating current or via a rectifier in the receiver, which converts it to direct current (DC). Since transmission efficiency increases with frequency, most systems use an electronic oscillator to produce higher frequency AC current that drives the transmitter coil. However, there are a small number of systems that operate at 50/60 Hz and directly apply AC mains current to the transmitter coil, like electric toothbrush charging stands.

6.5 Power Supply:

A power supply, sometimes called a power supply unit or PSU, is a system or equipment that provides energy, either electrically or otherwise, to a load or loads that are connected to it. When people talk about energy sources, the

word is usually used to describe electrical ones, not mechanical ones, and very never to describe others.

6.6 Circuit Diagram:

Fig:7 pin diagram

6.7 Power Supply Unit Block:

All digital circuits work only with low DC voltage. A power supply unit is required to provide the appropriate voltage supply. This unit consists of transformer, rectifier, filter and a regulator. AC voltage typically of 230Vrms is

connected to a transformer which steps that AC voltage down to the desired AC voltage level. A diode rectifier then provides a full wave rectified voltage that is initially filtered by a simple capacitor filter to produce a DC voltage.

Fig: 8 Power Supply Block Diagram

The main components used in the power supply unit are Transformer, Rectifier, Filter and Regulator. The 230V AC supply is converted into 9V AC supply through the transformer. The output of the transformer has the same frequency as in the input AC power. This AC power is converted into DC power through diodes. Here the bridge diode is used to convert AC supply to the DC power supply. This converted DC power supply has the ripple content and for normal operation of the circuit, the ripple content of the DC power supply should be as low as possible.

Because the ripple content of the power supply will reduce the life of the circuit. So to reduce the ripple content of the DC power supply, the large value of capacitance filter is used.

6.8 Switching Technique:

Soft switching begins one electrical parameter to zero (current or voltage) before the switch is turned on or off. This has benefits in terms of losses. The smooth resonant switching waveforms also minimize EMI. Common topologies like phase-shifted ZVS and LLC are soft switched only at turn-on.

Fig :9. switching techniques

For the simple reason that before switching happens, the term implies that the voltage or current within the transistor is 0. Turning the transistor on at zero VDS voltage for ZVS will decrease the turnon switching loss. In order to decrease the turn off switching loss, the transistor will be switched off for ZCS at zero ID current. Two or four transistors make up the majority of resonant circuit topologies. Turning transistors on and off repeatedly might leave them with residual energy, which can eventually lead to their failure. If this only occurs sometimes, a robust body diode should be plenty due to switching times. A fast body diode is necessary to ensure that all of the energy is removed from the transistor if this occurs continuously as a result of quick transition times.

The 6.9-volt battery: We need a deep cycle battery for our solar charging application. To counteract the damaging effects of continuous full-load use, deep cycle batteries use bigger plates and alternative chemistry. A lead-acid battery stores the electrical energy that is generated by the sun. The battery's rated capacity is the ampere-hour. Lead acid deep cycle batteries come in a few different varieties: Lead acid batteries have an efficiency range of 80-90% under ideal conditions. In most cases, keeping the battery fully charged will keep it running efficiently and prolong its life. Therefore, in order to avoid overcharging the battery or applying the incorrect voltage, a charge controller is used when solar panels are used for charging.

6.9 Winding coil:

According to Ampere's law, every conductor subjected to a current will generate a magnetic field around it in a circular pattern. The design of the coil is advantageous because it enhances the intensity of the magnetic field generated by a certain current. All of the magnetic fields from the individual wire turns meet in the middle of the coil, where they combine (superpose) to form a powerful field. The field strength is directly proportional to the number of turns of wire. On the other side, Faraday's law of induction states that a conductor, such a wire, will experience a voltage if the external magnetic flux changes. The induced voltage is enhanced when the wire is wound into a coil, since the field lines cross the circuit several times. This winding refers to the wire or conductor that makes up the coil. The magnetic axis or core region is the central hole in the coil. A turn denotes each individual loop of wire. Insulating the wire with a layer of nonconductive material, such enamel or plastic, is necessary in windings where the turns meet in order to stop electricity from flowing between the wires.

turns.

6.10 Power converter IGBT:

A minority-carrier device, the Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT) can handle a big bipolar current and has a high input impedance. A lot of designers think of an IGBT as a bipolar device that can be controlled by voltage; it has MOS input characteristics and bipolar output features. The IGBT combines the best features of the Power MOSFET and the BJT into a single device. This device combines Power MOSFET and BJT components into one integrated circuit. It takes the greatest parts of both to make the

perfect gadget. Applications in power electronics that need low noise and high dynamic range control, such as Pulse Width Modulated (PWM) servo and three-phase drives, are ideal for the IGBT. Other power circuits that need high switch repetition rates may also make advantage of it, such as Uninterruptible Power Supplies (UPS) and Switched-Mode Power Supplies (SMPS). By reducing the amount of audible noise and improving dynamic performance, IGBT is a great choice. It works just as well in circuits capable of resonant mode conversion. When it comes to reduced conduction loss and switching loss, optimised IGBTs are at your disposal. Compared to Power MOSFETs and BJTs, the primary benefits of an IGBT are: 1. Because to the design of the internal PNP thyristor, latchup might happen. An increase in the blocking voltage capabilities may be achieved with the help of an IGBT. Because a Power MOSFET's high working voltage necessitates an increasingly resistive and dense drift zone, the on-resistance grows dramatically as the breakdown voltage approaches. This is why the 6.12 MICROCONTROLLER (16F877A) high current power MOSFET was developed:

Microchip Technology's PIC series of microcontrollers is based on the PIC1650, which was created by General Instrument's Microelectronics Division. The PIC family has a modified Harvard design. "Peripheral Interface Controller" was the original meaning of the acronym PIC. Because of their inexpensive price, vast user base, abundance of application notes, availability of free or low-cost development tools, and ability to be serially programmed (and re-programmed with flash memory), PICs are popular with industrial developers and amateurs alike.

6.11 Pin Diagram:

Fig 9: PIC16F877a pin diagram.

6.12 Simulation Result:

Fig 10 : Simulation Model of WPT

Fig 12: Voltage and Current Waveform

RESULT AND CONCLUSION:

A LI-ION battery, an ultra capacitor bank, and a soft-switching full-bridge DC-DC converter make up an energy storage device. It seems to be the best option for EVs in the future. The gadget is designed to make it possible for the car to accelerate and decelerate more forcefully while wasting as little energy and damaging the battery pack as possible. The development of a simulation-based electrical modelling approach allows for an effective analysis of the performance of soft-switching inverters. In addition to providing accurate stress and switching loss predictions, it expands the scope of EMI noise analysis to the higher frequency area. We have completed three main modelling jobs. The first step in developing the IGBT model is to suggest a new method of parameter extraction that would solve the problems with the current, too complex scheme. Second, in order to determine the half-bridge modules' internal parasitic characteristics, a measuring technique based on impedance is created. As a result, the power density will rise. Traditional circuits are also used to compare efficiency. This will also show how the suggested converter's efficiency has been enhanced. The [1]

correct switching of the load was used to attain power factor.

REFERENCES:

The following is a reference to an article published in 2013 by Richardson in the *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Review*: "Electric vehicles and the electric grid: a review of modelling approaches, impacts, and renewable energy integration" (pp. 247-254). [2] In the article "Electric vehicles and smart grid interaction: a review on vehicle to grid and renewable energy sources integration" was published in 2014 in the *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Review* and includes the works of F. Mwasilu, J. Justo, E. Kim, and others. the third "Demand response management via real-time electricity price control in smart grids" (*IEEE Journal of Specialised Areas*, 2013, 31, 7, pp. 1268-1280), by Qian, L.P., Zhang, Y.J.A., Huang, J., et al. [4] "Integrating price responsive demand into the unit commitment problem" (*IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 2014, 5, 6, pp. 2757-2765), written by Tumuluru, V.K., Huang, Z., and Tsang, D.H.K.